

Chinese Language Teaching as a Second Language: Immersion Teaching

Lee Bih Ni, Kiu Su Na

Abstract—This paper discusses the Chinese Language Teaching as a Second Language by focusing on Immersion Teaching. Researchers used narrative literature review to describe the current states of both art and science in focused areas of inquiry. Immersion teaching comes with a standard that teachers must reliably meet. Chinese language-immersion instruction consists of language and content lessons, including functional usage of the language, academic language, authentic language, and correct Chinese sociocultural language. Researchers used narrative literature reviews to build a scientific knowledge base. Researchers collected all the important points of discussion, and put them here with reference to the specific field where this paper is originally based on. The findings show that Chinese Language in immersion teaching is not like standard foreign language classroom; immersion setting provides more opportunities to teach students colloquial language than academic. Immersion techniques also introduce a language's cultural and social contexts in a meaningful and memorable way. It is particularly important that immersion teachers connect classwork with real-life experiences. Immersion also includes more elements of discovery and inquiry based learning than do other kinds of instructional practices. Students are always and consistently interpreted the conclusions and context clues.

Keywords—A second language, Chinese language teaching, immersion teaching, instructional strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

CHILDREN learn their first language subconsciously with relative ease and little if any pressure. When all conditions are normal, most children learn the basic structure and vocabulary of their first language in the first four years of their lives. This language continues to grow through life in sophistication and complexity depends primarily on the level of educational children eventually and uses appropriate language. Generally, children who succeed in acquiring their first language tend to speech marked by accents and expressions regional area where they grow.

People can learn any number of languages over their lifetime from failure experience in different degrees in the process of learning another language. Adults often complain that the target language (second / foreign language) is difficult to understand or pronounce. Anyone who has ever seriously tried to master another language knows that it is time-consuming and challenging task. However, research and experience show that the area was only affected most negatively by the start of the "late" is a reference to the study of language; in other words, a speaker of a second language

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can often be recognized by accent caused by the characteristics of the first phonology. Some students may have a second language "disguise" themselves as native speakers of the target language. The acquisition of the communicative and functional purposes of language is, in most circumstances, far more important than a perfect native accent [1].

If one considers the study of language mean just memorization of vocabulary and sentence structures with "good" designation, the overall effort was doomed to failure from the start. The study of another language is much broader than that. Readers should refer to [2] for a simple and clear explanation in writing from the language we need to know in order to teach the language. In short, the linguistic component of students and teachers need to investigate is the syntax (sentence structure), phonology (sound system), lexicon (vocabulary), semantics (meaning), and pragmatic (use). Language is the whole complex, requiring mastery of commitment to learn to live, especially if the standard sought is an educated native speaker. Learning a language is a process that takes time under the best of circumstances, when students are motivated and have everything available to help him to achieve his goal.

It is important to note that language learning is not a linguistic phenomenon. It is influenced by a number of social and psychological factors, all of which are intertwined in a unique way in the case of each student. Previous experience as students learn general and specific image of themselves as language learners will decide how the learning tasks seen, whether, for example, would seem impossible or can do. An existing knowledge, attitude, personality, style, skill, and motivation, to mention a few, are all factors associated with the result of the study of language. (For a thorough overview of the process of second language acquisition, see [1]). The most important element, however, which appears to determine the relative failure or success of language acquisition, is learning environment itself.

II. LANGUAGE TEACHING

A. Review Stage

Languages taught and learned in various places, some in informal settings, and others in formal contexts, such as classrooms. It is common knowledge that no matter which method is used; the second language students achieve mastery of the target language to varying degrees. People are capable of learning any number of languages during their lifetime but many experience failure to different degrees in the process of learning other languages. This is the result of combine these factors briefly above, completion of pedagogical methods that

students have faced. Generally, it could be said that most people learn to communicate basic information through conversation in the target language in the first few years of active language learning (provided that there are opportunities to use the language to create personal meaning). It is important to note that the mere exposure or contact with the target language in many cases not enough to cause productive language skills [3]. The results showed that language learners can improve their speaking proficiency to a significant extent through exposure to audiovisual mass media technologies in informal setting. In contrast, for the sake of comprehension and communication, social interaction in English may hinder the development of language learners [23]. The fact that an informal learning experience might give the learner an opportunity to experience authentic language in a real context that may enrich his or her learning experience in a way that cannot be achieved by using a textbook, has traditionally not been given much regard [24].

The critical period hypothesis states that the first few years of life is the crucial time in which an individual can acquire a first language if presented with enough encouragement. Adult learners are also more affected by the type of input they have experienced and often control the quantity and quality, which means that they can either be required to "eliminate" the language if it is, or they can look for opportunities to accelerate the learning process. Adult learning is a process that is quite conscious. Most language learners seem to be able to clearly state whether they are "good" in language learning or not, whether they seem to enjoy it or not, and whether they want to continue or not. Because adults have cognitive tool available to them which they use to learn other subjects in general, the same study skills can help them identify personal learning pathways for effective and meaningful to the acquisition of a second language [4]. Students are attracted to informal education because it provides them with an opportunity to feel recognized for their own worth in settings in which students can influence and control the pace, as well as the content, of their learning. Many feel that they can contribute in these settings in their own way: that they are valued for what they have to contribute and feel a greater ownership of the learning experience [25]. Generally speaking, it can be stated that most individuals learn to communicate basic information through a conversation in the target language in the first few years of active language study (provided that there are opportunities to use the language to create personal meaning). It is important to note that mere exposure or contact with the target language in most cases is not sufficient to result in productive language skills [26].

Cummins in his classic work has separated language skills into two major categories of proficiency [5]. Basic Interpersonal Communication Skills (ICS) usually require several years to develop. This means that the student is able to speak the language of every day affairs and often appear to be eligible users for that language, fluent and able to respond to the stimulus of the most concrete. However, according to Cummins, Cognitive Academic Language Proficiency (CALP), a capability that allows students to discuss and

review the concept, academic materials in a second language takes several years, which is the result of years of advanced studies in the target language. In other words, even if a person is perfectly capable of carrying on a conversation in the target language, the same individual may not be equipped with the skills needed to study the abstract concepts in the same language. Which requires knowledge of the academic structure of complex sentences, rhetorical understanding of written and spoken in the language, and have a refined sophisticated vocabulary. The level of language proficiency can be achieved only through academic study directed and, therefore, can be achieved only through hard work, native included.

Working adults often have a need to acquire new knowledge as soon as possible; again, the language put timetables on their own and tend not to respond to "cramming." Language needs time alone, learning a language is, of course, a process. This process can be speeded up by an intensive English language program in cases where the focus is solely on the systematic study of the language for a few hours each day. Students who, for example, have the opportunity to attend intensive language courses may be developed more quickly and take a great leap of progress than those who do not have the time or resources to do the same [6].

B. Instructional Strategies: Successful Approaches to Immersion Teaching

Language immersion program presents a range of opportunities and challenges for practitioners. Many language teachers welcome the opportunity to create an immersive language environment where students are able to achieve the level of competence and fluency in the target language, and learn the academic language and also every day. However, due to immersion teachers not only teach the language but also teach other academic subjects, they have a number of additional issues that need to be considered. In any immersion programs, language and subject partner are equally important, and the most successful approach to balance them equally. In this way, successful immersion teaching is good teaching pinnacle. Form an interdisciplinary study of the possibility of education in general. Immersion teacher starts from the assumption that the barriers between the various fields of study are to some extent artificial, and that the direction of the exciting, dynamic, and effective in all subject areas contain many of the same core elements. By their nature, immersion program shows all the knowledge and experience of each other.

Immersion teachers must clearly understand what content should be taught at each grade level. They should be familiar with "input is understandable," which emphasizes that students should be exposed to words and new patterns in the context of facilitating the understanding and assimilation. Teachers need to consistently weave language together with ordinary words and new information, so that students continually develop their language proficiency. In this way, the acquisition of language in immersion programs closely

mimic the natural learning curve for the first language, where children are constantly encouraged to assimilate the language and meaning of words is not recognized and expressions. Immersion also includes more elements discovery and research-based learning rather than do other types of teaching practices. Students should always and consistently interpret the conclusions and context clues [7].

Immersion programs are equipped with high standards that teachers must be fulfilled. Language-immersion instruction consists of language and content of the lesson, including use of language function, academic language, the original language and the language sociocultural appropriate. Unlike standard foreign language classroom, setting immersion provide more opportunities to teach students colloquial language than academic. Immersion techniques are also introduced social language and cultural context in ways that are meaningful and unforgettable. It is important that immersion teachers connect with the real experience of the working class. For example, students need to learn when to say, "what" and when to say, "it's a pleasure to meet you, sir." They must understand when he said, "it's freezing in here," and when it is noted, "The temperature today is fifteen degrees below the average mean temperature for this time of year." By using various communication styles, educators instill hope that the students will use the language in real life situations as well as in education.

III. THE TOP FIVE IMMERSION TEACHING SKILLS

A. The Ability to Use Visuals, Gestures, Body Language, Expressions, Modeling, and Movement to Complement Verbal Cues

For students to learn a new language in meaningful contexts, teachers must use every instructional strategy available to them, including the use of actual objects (realia), pictures, videos, and gestures to express meaning. This will allow students to develop comprehension without direct explanation. The ability to use visuals, gestures, body language, expressions, modeling, and movement to complement verbal cues is need for students' experiential learning. For students to learn a new language in meaningful contexts, teachers must use every instructional strategy available to them, including the use of actual objects (realia), pictures, videos, and gestures to express meaning. This will allow students to develop comprehension without direct explanation [13].

B. The Ability to Motivate Students to Stay in the Target Language

Students who are still new to Chinese should be encouraged to respond to teacher prompts and questions in English if they are not yet able to express themselves in Chinese. As students get older, however, they should be increasingly encouraged to use Chinese exclusively in all of the classes conducted in Chinese. As students' progress toward higher levels of proficiency, they should also be discouraged from mixing the two languages, and urged to stay in one or the other language, as appropriate. The ability to motivate students to stay in the

target language is vital for learning language. Students who are still new to Chinese should be encouraged to respond to teacher prompts and questions in English if they are not yet able to express themselves in Chinese. As students get older, however, they should be increasingly encouraged to use Chinese exclusively in all of the classes conducted in Chinese. As students' progress toward higher levels of proficiency, they should also be discouraged from mixing the two languages, and urged to stay in one or the other language, as appropriate [13].

C. The Ability to Ask Open-Ended Questions

Effective teachers, no matter the subject or setting, steer clear of questions that elicit only "yes or no" answers. Instead, they challenge students' thinking, nudging their higher-order cognitive skills and giving ample time to articulate each response. In immersion classrooms, it is especially important that teachers encourage students to give longer and more varied replies. For instance, they can ask students to expand upon or support their answers with examples or evidence. Following up in this way, it helps students practice a variety of expressions and to incorporate fresh words and patterns into their productive repertoire. Open-ended questions offer children the opportunity to freely express feelings, motives and ideas. A question like, "What color is that block?" evokes a one-word answer. But an open-ended question such as, "Tell me about the blocks you are using," encourages a child to describe the blocks or explain what he or she is doing. There is no right or wrong answer. Asking open-ended questions give children opportunities to use an expanded vocabulary. An answer to an open-ended question gives us a window into what the child is thinking and feeling. The response is sometimes wonderfully creative. In explaining or describing, children also use language more fully [18].

Children's learning naturally loops through a cycle of wonder, exploration, discovery, reflection, and more wonder, leading them on to increasingly complex knowledge and sophisticated thinking. The power of open-ended questions comes from the way these questions tap into that natural cycle, inviting children to pursue their own curiosity about how the world works. Open-ended questions show children that their teachers trust them to have good ideas, think for themselves, and contribute in valuable ways. The resulting sense of autonomy, belonging, and competence leads to engagement and deep investment in classroom activities [19].

D. The Ability to Regularly Assess Students' Comprehension and Skills Development

Teachers need to monitor students' understanding through questioning techniques and formative assessments. They should also be consistently pushing students to use new words and expressions, more complex language structures, and more culturally appropriate language in their interactions and responses. Teachers should encourage students to use more specific vocabulary, as opposed to generic expressions, as they continue to develop their skills [8]. One of the critical realities for most underachieving students is that very often they are

not able to identify the key focus of the learning, or discipline concepts, to be studied in a unit of study or other text used. This lack of understanding inhibits their comprehension, resulting in little or no motivation, which is exacerbated by their feeling a lack of confidence in their competence to achieve. Confidence is the result of knowing what to do and believing you have the skills and abilities to meet those expectations. If we want to reverse this cycle of underachievement and the accompanying feeling of incompetence, we have to provide mediation strategies for students to feel confident that they understand what we are teaching and have the skills to communicate their understanding [20].

Comprehension is the ability to construct meaning. Reading comprehension is the ability to construct meaning using text [21]. There is no getting around the fact that 90% of what we use to teach students is done with text. Given this reality, we may not be reading teachers, but if we expect students to learn from text, then we must be teachers of text comprehension. The texts we use in our disciplines require a "literacy" of the discipline in order for students to comprehend them. Literacy is the ability to construct, communicate, and create meaning in many forms of representation (e.g., writing, math symbols, musical notation, and visual art) [22]. In discipline literacy students must have the frame of reference to know the technical terms that enable them to understand how the professionals in the discipline think and what they do: e.g., what do good writers do? What do mathematicians do? Literacy of the discipline requires fluency in its vocabulary and being able to construct and communicate meaning using the organizational structures of the discipline [22].

E. The Ability to Think Strategically about the Various Types of Student Interactions and to Vary Them, Promoting a Dynamic Learning Environment

Teachers can mix the following types of interactions: teacher-students, student-student, whole group, and small groups. In small-group and project-based settings, teachers need to carefully evaluate the makeup of the various groups. Each student should work with various people in the class, but there should also be opportunities for long-term and on going student interactions.

Immersion instruction differs from other types of language learning because students learn a variety of subjects in the target language. In the atmosphere of Chinese immersion, students learn content through China, and China learned as they learn the content. Balancing the two main goals of immersion is an important consideration when designing, implementing, and developing immersion program.

Two sets of curriculum will drive what happens in classrooms every day: things (content) language and literacy curriculum and curriculum China. In both cases, the decision on what students need to achieve comes from national standards and / or other countries [9].

States and school districts have been guided by national standards in almost every discipline. Although national standards have become a strong point of reference in shaping

the content of the curriculum, national standards adherence has voluntarily. Conversely, many states have developed mandatory standards almost parallel some, if not all, of voluntary national standard. Standard state sets expectations for what all students in the state need to know and can do. These standards are the basis for state-level assessment administered at certain grade levels throughout the country. Schools and school districts, in turn, have used both voluntary national standards and standards government mandated curriculum as a foundation document that describes what students should learn. The curriculum, therefore, help teachers know what to teach.

Regions and schools changed their approach to certain subjects in the syllabus given grade level. For example, a science unit on plants may be found in the third grade in a local school in the fourth grade and in other countries. Math topics such as number sense, multiplication, and division may be taught in the same grade at two schools, but the level of expectation and time may vary. These differences make it difficult for teachers to collaborate and share the marinade ingredients for content area instruction. In recent years, however, almost all states have chosen to participate in a national education initiative that will bring much greater consistency across the state, district and school. This new "common core" content, in turn, will make it more likely that the immersion program will be more consistent, so that students in different locations will reach the same level of skills. Hopefully, these consistencies will facilitate the sharing of resources and teaching Chinese immersion [9].

IV. EFFECTIVE TEACHING STRATEGIES FOR IMMERSION TEACHERS

District Immersion teachers need to provide their students with a structured learning environment that attends to language development and content-area knowledge development while consistently using the immersion language. Students benefit from frequent opportunities to use the immersion language in the context of teacher use of multisensory experiences supported by visual aids, gestures and manipulatives. Successful immersion teachers use predictable instructional routines and patterned language for transitions. By developing a variable repertoire of instructional strategies, teachers can help students understand both language and content.

Instructional strategies can be broken into four specific teacher tasks:

1. make input comprehensible;
2. provide opportunities for language output;
3. enhance the comprehensibility of readings; and
4. develop a system for providing constructive feedback.

Making input comprehensible begins with simplification of language and using language known as "caretaker speech" or "foreigner talk" in which the following are evident: slower speech rate, clear enunciation, controlled vocabulary/idioms, high frequency words, controlled sentence length/complexity, and rephrasing to promote clarity and understanding. While this is important at the beginning stages of immersion, as

immersion students' progress in the language, they need more complex input so that they develop a full range of language competency [14].

Swain has taken the notion of input one step farther with her suggestion that students acquire language most meaningfully when they also have the opportunity for comprehensible "output." That is, they need to have a setting in which they are given many opportunities to produce new forms and to communicate, as well as settings in which their attempts at communication are valued and shaped to make them acceptable and understandable. Students need these opportunities to produce new forms, so that they can correct and adjust their hypotheses about the language. Providing opportunities for the students to produce appropriate language output is currently one of the major challenges of immersion teaching [15].

A third instructional strategy focuses on enhancing the comprehensibility of readings. Previewing new structures and vocabulary and helping students make connections between the new vocabulary/concepts and the old allows students to draw on their background knowledge to aid comprehension. Employing techniques such as advance organizers, story mapping, story grammars and semantic mapping are also recommended pre-reading strategies. Taking time to discuss the title and the broader context of a text including the year and place of publication, the author, the format, etc. can help students understand the bigger picture. Based on this wide lens view, students can begin to formulate questions about the text or make predictions about the story. Encouraging students to draw meaning from the pictures in the reading or additional or related visuals can also help text comprehension. Following a text in the immersion language with the text in English may also assist comprehension. Remember that students enjoy reading what they themselves or other students have written.

A common problem in the output of immersion students is that errors are abundant and constructive feedback, especially in response to errors, tends to be sporadic and inconsistent. Swain attributes this to the fact that the focus in immersion teaching tends to be entirely meaning-oriented and does not pay attention to the form of the message [16]. This problem is exacerbated by the fact that in the early stages of immersion programs, immersion teachers are expressly told that excessive reliance on grammar instruction and error correction are to be avoided because these techniques short circuit the learning process [17]. Some recent research on error correction in immersion contexts has been conducted by Roy Lyster and colleagues in Canada and will be highlighted in the next issue of the newsletter [17].

Some recommended teaching strategies for increasing opportunities for language output include guiding students from more simple to more complex responses. For example, one might begin with a question in which the acceptable student response might be to point, then to answer with a "yes" or a "no," then a single word answer to an either/or question, or a single word answer to a why- question (who, what, when, where, why, which), and finally a full sentence answer to an open-ended question. Other "output" strategies

might include teaching students prefabricated chunks of language such as in songs, rhymes, poems and chants. Teachers are often inclined to do most of the talking in the classroom; therefore, it is important to focus on allowing students more opportunities to use the language and extending wait time to refrain from immediately supplying students with the answers. Interactive partner and cooperative learning tasks can also be effectively used to increase student output.

V. CONTENT LEARNING IN CHINESE IMMERSION PROGRAMS

District and school level students' curriculum determine what content needs to be studied. The curriculum for instruction content-area teachers are usually not developed by individual, although the content is taught through the medium of new languages such as China. Immersion students are expected to study the curriculum content, the same area and reached the same level as that of the control students who are not in immersion programs.

For almost two decades, states and school districts have been guided by national standards in almost every discipline. While national standards have been a powerful point of reference in shaping curriculum content, adherence to national standards has been voluntary. These variances made it difficult for immersion teachers to collaborate and share materials for content area instruction. In recent years, however, almost all states have chosen to participate in a national education initiative that will bring far greater consistency across states, districts, and schools [9].

Program designers determine how much time will be spent learning content in English and how much time will be spent in Chinese. In most Chinese immersion programs in the United States, some subjects are taught in English and others in Chinese, although these subjects may vary by grade level. In some programs, program designers have arranged the schedule so that all subjects are taught in both languages. The decision on which subjects should be taught in a language that is likely to include consideration of the following questions [9]:

1. Which subjects at a particular grade level are most likely to be accessible to students given their current level of Chinese proficiency?
2. Which subjects at a particular grade level present language-rich opportunities for student to develop their oral proficiency in Chinese?
3. How heavily does a content area depend on literacy? Which subjects are most suitable for students' level of Chinese literacy, so that they learn content-area material at or above expectations? How well does a content area allow for students to improve their Chinese literacy?
4. How will the program ensure that students are prepared to deal with academic terminology in English as well as in Chinese so that they are able to demonstrate content-area performance? They will also need to segue to instruction in these subjects taught in English in later grades.
5. Are there available resources (teachers, print and non-print instructional materials) to ensure high-quality instruction in these subjects?

VI. CHINESE LANGUAGE AND LITERACY CURRICULA

As the curriculum for other subjects, Chinese and Literacy curriculum is based on national standards and state. However, it is unlikely that significant already curriculum at the school or district that specifically determines what teachers should teach and what students need to learn. In fact, many veteran immersion programs in Chinese, France and Spain, only begin to consider the development of a curriculum for Chinese language and literacy.

In the last decade in the United States immersion teaching, educators can only be used while the content of teaching a second language school, believe that students will absorb a new language. This, of course is successful. However, from time to time immersion teachers have found that while students can easily understand the lessons and express themselves in their second language, they were inaccurate or the author. The ways in which they expressed ideas are not really fluent; they do not communicate smooth like a native. Immersion educators began to look for ways to improve the model they have already resulted in a higher level of control than other forms of foreign language teaching in schools in the United States [9].

Coupled with the aim of improving current practices in immersion education are unique challenges for languages that do not use the Roman alphabet as a writing system. With its rapid growth and the recent Chinese immersion program has questions about literacy [10]:

- 1) How well do students need to read and write Chinese?
- 2) How do we set reasonable goals for literacy students by the amount of time in the school day allocated to Chinese?
- 3) What strategies will help speakers of English to Chinese literacy?
- 4) How well the strategy used for teaching English literacy in America's schools adapt to literacy teaching in China?

Which aspects of literacy development we can expect to move from Chinese to English and vice versa?

VII. ARTICULATION, ALIGNMENT, AUTHENTICITY, ADOPTION, AND ADAPTION

No matter how much time studying languages, teaching contexts - whether formal or informal - must contain certain key components to foster success. Van Lier argues that language learning efficiency is enhanced by understanding their own learning what he is doing and why (awareness), can make a personal decision about process (autonomy), and introduced to the materials that are relevant, meaningful and practical (validity). Students, in other words, must be mentally in the learning situation and must have the desire to put forth the effort to acquire another language [11].

Before looking for a suitable material immersion school must have a curriculum specified in place. Regardless of the entrance or end point, which, in sequence without interruption curriculum that connects from the lowest to the highest levels of the program should be ensured? This articulation of the school curriculum should be based on strong alignment with

the standards set for each subject area, and also for the development of language in both Chinese and English.

Many countries are aligning with developed new Common Core State Standards in English and math. Some states also aligning social studies, science, and world languages standard. In the next few years, all areas of the curriculum need not only to align with national standards, but also the Common Core State Standards.

After a curriculum that is aligned and set in place, an immersion school can begin to identify materials teaching and resources. Materials authentic Chinese made a great impact by authentic, we mean material created by the natives to native speakers. If teachers are looking for something that is too difficult to use when the students, they need to check to see if the content, topic, or merit adapt text. When adopting and adapting sub-turn from these materials, teachers need to carefully select their content based on student readiness, interests, and learning styles [12].

A. Selection Criteria

Whether purchased or provided by the teachers' program, the ingredients for the marinade students must meet the following criteria [12].

Rich content is including content specific subjects such as math, science, biology, people, places and:

- a) Exciting and attractive content
- b) The story same with the English language
- c) Stories relating to student life
- d) The material reflects the Chinese culture and other cultures
- e) Reading that have specific learning objectives language
- f) Read on to learn and for fun

There are some strong advantages to teachers create their own materials. Because the best teachers understand curriculum, they were careful to match the material to the needs of students. Teachers will have a sense of ownership satisfying, and they can continue to improve materials for teaching the next round. Since most of the materials can be stored and shared in digital, teachers can pool their resources and also organize groups to share their materials. It is also possible to purchase materials from publishers based in Singapore, Hong Kong, and China, which often have Chinese editions to students. While this sounds like a simple solution, it involves some trial and error potential expensive. There is no way to guarantee the right of finding content, age-appropriate, and the level of difficulty for your students. Sometimes, the school bought a lot of ingredients to find something useful. The law is safe even if the bet is limited; support materials can be the most time consuming to detect.

B. Textbooks

When selecting textbooks, there are many considerations. Some areas require the same textbook is used by both Chinese and English classrooms. In this case, materials are translated by a Chinese teacher. Some programs teach the same content twice, in Chinese with a text book, in English with others. Teachers absorption has done translation may be willing to

share their work.

If materials are available, for a long sequence of more grades, it is the responsibility of the teacher to choose appropriate content at the right time, and is not bound by the order and sequence set in textbook itself [12].

C. Technology

As in many areas, effective use of technology can make a major impact on the Chinese immersion program. As teachers play a key role in adopting a new program or an offer digital, they must consider how new tools will engage students, enhance comprehension hear them, improve their stroke order when writing, and expose they sound authentic. Diversity is merely help; as different students respond to different activities. Here are some possibilities to consider. Individual white boards, combined with transparent sleeves can be an inexpensive way to efficiently engage students like Sudoku, pair work, and group work. iPad has a lot of potential to augment or replace technologies such as Smartboard. Multimedia or web cartoons and application support literacy and comprehension. Free technologies such as Skype can be brought in to connect students [12].

VIII. CONCLUSION

In Chinese language immersion teaching, three things happen simultaneously. Understanding these three areas will help educators develop and identify the materials and resources they will need to support the program. First, build content knowledge, including core concepts in mathematics, science, social studies, and so on. Second, students learn content areas in Chinese; social and academic language is introduced at the same time. Third, students are conducted in pre-reading and pre-writing, then read and write. Chinese Language Teaching as a Second Language by focusing on Immersion Teaching can be practiced by teachers to non-Chinese students in Chinese primary schools in Malaysia. When educators identify the materials they need to save another three rules in mind: the materials should be appropriate to the age, grade, and stage language. For example, some materials developed for children cannot be age-appropriate. In the school environment should be a variety of books, reading material graded, old books and reading materials are free. Chinese language immersion instruction focuses on language development and literacy exercise some or all of the following steps:

- Set clear performance goals that align with the metrics commonly used in the specified grade level.
- For each grade level, reflect the level of proficiency of students in terms of observable and measurable and align the "can do" statements with control targets.
- Develop language and literacy activities that determine the means of language / literacy students will learn to demonstrate that they "can do" what to expect on their grade level.
- Indicate how the elements of language and literacy (vocabulary, grammatical structure, language function, type, etc.) will be taught in each unit of content taught in

Chinese or English / literacy separate lesson.

- Assess students both formal and informal to make sure expectations that trying to set.

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